

NATIONAL VARIATIONS IN LEGAL TERMINOLOGY. THE BRITISH AND AMERICAN PERSPECTIVE

Nicoleta BAGHICI, Assistant Professor, MA
("Alec Russo" Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

nicoleta.baghici@usarb.md, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6654-7397>

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The aim of the research is to investigate the cultural specificity underlying the composition of British and American legal terminologies. Despite a common origin in the Anglo-Saxon and Roman legal traditions, British Legal Terminology (BLT) and American Legal Terminology (ALT) have undergone particular developments due to various socio-political, historical, and cultural conditions. The study analyzes distinctions in taxonomic structures, paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations, and the use of proprial terms. Special attention is given to the role of internationalisms and terminological synonymy, revealing how extralinguistic factors influence the evolution and structure of legal language. The findings underscore the dynamic interplay between linguistic universality and national legal identity.